

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF THE LANGUAGE OF THE INTERNET AND SOCIAL NETWORKS

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Abstract. The expansion of the scope of interdisciplinary communication in world linguistics is an important factor in the emergence and development of new knowledge. The integration of disciplines is gaining importance in finding solutions to problems that have arisen in new areas and directions. The study of the linguistic characteristics of the Internet language and social networks has become one of the most pressing issues in world linguistics. The Internet and social networks have a significant impact on people's activities, learning, communication, thinking and emotional state in the modern era. The creation of the Internet has served the development of all areas.

Keywords: Internet language, social network language, "Netlish", "Weblish", "Cyberlanguage", "e-talk", websites, blogs, chat groups, connotation.

Introduction. The Internet (from Latin: inter - inter and net - network) is a global and publicly accessible collection of computer networks that exchange information via the standard Internet Protocol (IP). The Internet system appeared in the 60s of the 20th century. At that time, at the initiative of the US Department of Defense, computers began to be connected to telephone networks. Initially, such activities were carried out as part of the research of the Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA). In 1964, the ARPANET Internet network, consisting of 4 networks, was created. These studies coincided with the outbreak of the Cold War. As can be seen from the above and similar data, Internet networks were first used in the military sphere, and later became popular among scientists and the population. The creation of the World Wide Web in Switzerland further popularized the Internet and created the possibility of direct transmission of information in the media.

Information services for connecting to the Internet in Uzbekistan began to be provided in 1997. Initially, providers such as Naytov (<http://www.naytov.com>), Uznet (<http://www.uznet.net> (archived at the Wayback Machine on 2013-02-16)) or Eastlink (<http://www.eastlink.uz> (archived at the Wayback Machine on 2020-06-12)) began

operating (1999). The Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to organize the development of a program to ensure access to international information systems of the Internet" (2001) serves to establish Uzbekistan's position in this regard on an international scale. The national data transmission network in Uzbekistan consists of the UzPAK State Company and the UzNET network¹. A total of 5.56 billion people are using the internet as of the beginning of 2025, resulting in a coverage rate of 67.9 percent². One of the main functions of the Internet is communication. According to statistics, a large part of the population aged 16 to 34 uses the Internet for social communication. Language is the basis of communication. The language used on the Internet is a new form of natural language, that is, Internet language. Internet language is a language that differs from ordinary spoken and written language and has its own characteristics, style and patterns.

Research methodology. Internet language emerged as a result of people's need to transmit and receive information faster, and we currently call it netspeak³. The Internet is a social invention. If it is a revolution, it will probably be a linguistic revolution⁴. The creation of the Internet is truly a social discovery and ranks higher than other inventions. This is because, while other inventions belong to a certain narrow circle, the Internet has accumulated information from all inventions and their related fields. The Internet is a means of establishing communication between people on a large scale and quickly. The basis of Internet communication is language. Internet language has caused significant changes in human activity, culture, spirituality, thinking and speech. Internet language has created a new style in all branches of linguistics. Neologisms are rapidly entering linguistics through the Internet and are also undergoing a process of determinization. Internet language is a reflection of natural language. Internet language has its own style in the communication of people of different nations, regions, cultures and worldviews. The term Internet language is called differently in different languages.

The term "Internet language" is sometimes referred to as "Netlish", "Weblish", "Cyberlanguage", "e-talk" or "CMC (Computer-Mediated Communication)". Each of these has its own connotations⁵. These terms are mainly English-specific; in Uzbek, it is more effective to use the terms "internet language" or "internet linguistics".

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Internet>

² <https://daryo.uz/2025/02/17/odamlarning-qancha-vaqti-internetda-otmoqda>

³ Bija Alexandra PERSPECTIVES ON THE INFLUENCE OF THE INTERNET ON LANGUAGE// JOURNAL OF ROMANIAN LITERARY STUDIES no. 18/2019

⁴ D.Crystal,2004

⁵ David Crystal Language and the Internet. Cambridge-2004. b-9

Results and discussion. Internet linguistics is considered a science that studies the manifestation of language in the electronic environment. Internet linguistics studies new language styles and forms created by the Internet. Internet linguistics can develop in four perspectives: sociolinguistics, pedagogy, stylistics and applied linguistics. If we talk about communication and conversation, we cannot do without mentioning the term discourse. We cannot say that Internet linguistics is relevant only for a certain narrow circle⁶. Because a new form of linguistics called Internet linguistics has made a fundamental shift in all areas of science, society, politics, and so on, it is equally important for all areas such as jurisprudence, economics, medicine, and production. Since language units and speech act as the main tool in Internet linguistics, it shows that changes in all areas are related to the field of linguistics. Communication on the Internet and social networks has both synchronous and asynchronous forms, and at the same time serves as an important tool for people to relax, study, work, and personal communication.

On the Internet, language is expressed in various forms, both verbally and in writing:

- SMS messages (tweets, comments, blogs, etc.)
- Video messages
- Audio messages
- E-mail
- Main images and videos

Of these, the most widespread and most popular Internet network, which has become a major source of income, is blogs.

“Blogs are the beginning of a new stage in the evolution of written language”⁷.

We have not yet fully classified "Internet language" and incorporated it into the system of traditional linguistic registers. This field is still new and in its formative stages⁸. The Internet and social networks serve as a real field of practice for linguistics. Since the information in them belongs to the state or an individual, the possibility of free use and research of information is limited. Nevertheless, there is an opportunity to study the properties of language units in openly expressed text, audio and visual information, such as variability, flexibility, sociality, and its linguistic capabilities. The Internet and social networks have created an opportunity for people around the world to communicate with each other through common knowledge on a large scale. Internet

⁶ M. N. Imanova Some Linguistic Features of Internet Texts//International Journal of Social Science And Human Research. Volume 06 Issue 10 October 2023

⁷ David Crystal (2005). "The Scope of Internet Linguistics" . paper presented at the American Association for the Advancement of Science meeting.

⁸ David Crystal Language and the Internet. Cambridge-2004. p.22

language serves the development of written speech. This language not only serves the development of linguistics, but can also cause some negative changes and losses in linguistics. It creates linguistic problems along with problems related to pornography, extremism, copyright, security, privacy, defamation, and crime. As a result of communication around the world via the Internet and social networks, certain changes are occurring in language and culture as a result of imitation or imitation. The language of the Internet and social networks can be said to be a language formed at the intersection of all languages that do not have their own standards. The style, grammar, semantics, punctuation, emojis, abbreviations of the Internet language are different in e-mail, chats, social networks, blogs, web pages, and they have a special individuality. The types of social networks have their own style and conventions, depending on the formal and informal appearance, information content, type of mass group and user potential. In particular, posts on types of social networks such as Twitter and Facebook, although personal and short, have social and linguistic conventions. In short, the language of social networks, although not fully subject to traditional language standards, has its own style and form, and this style and form are learned and mastered by users.

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